

Research about semi-automation solutions that generate the BIM model from point cloud data

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Abstract

This thesis explores the application of semi-automation solutions in generating Building Information Modelling (BIM) models from point cloud data. The aim is to enhance the efficiency and accuracy of the Scan to BIM process by leveraging advanced software combined with familiar BIM processes. The research investigates the transition from conventional BIM practices to Scan to BIM, highlighting the incorporation of 3D laser scanning technology and point cloud data into the BIM workflow. The study examines the challenges, benefits, and future directions of utilizing semi-automation in the Scan to BIM process. It focuses on factors affecting data quality, including data collection preparation, acquisition techniques, and data processing methods. Additionally, the research discusses the role of defining the Level of Development (LOD) before initiating the Scan to BIM process. The findings contribute to developing best practices, methodologies, and guidelines for architecture, engineering, and construction professionals, enabling them to optimize the Scan to BIM workflow and generate accurate as-built BIM models.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/yGzSjctUS9I>

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